

AI-DRIVEN SELF ADAPTION UNLOCKING INTELLIGENT CONFIGURATION MANAGEMENT

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Abstract— Within the domain of software development, a key challenge revolves around swiftly finding and fixing bugs. This paper introduces an API that smoothly fits into existing software development processes placing a significant emphasis on improving bug detection. Our approach identifies potential coding issues rooted in real-world experiences. Enhanced by Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) analysis, the API ensures meticulous bug localization. This speeds up the bug-fixing process all while adhering to established coding standards. The incorporation of Sequence-to-Sequence (Seq2Seq) models introduces automated code correction, substantially enhancing the efficiency of software development. Through the early identification of bugs and automated correction mechanisms, this approach promotes an improvement in the overall quality of code, ensuring a continuous trajectory of software enhancement.

Keywords— Abstract Syntax Tree(AST), Automated code correction, bug detection, code quality, feature selection

1 INTRODUCTION

In the realm of software development, the inevitability of encountering software bugs persists. The continuous expansion of software scale and intricacy has led to a notable surge in the daily reporting of bugs. A striking example is the Eclipse software, widely used and acknowledged for receiving approximately 200 bug reports daily from users, particularly after a new version is released ^[2]. Solving these software vulnerabilities requires a significant time and effort commitment ^[7]. Recognizing the imperative need to enhance bug resolution efficiency, this paper endeavours to propose an innovative approach in the context of bug tracking systems.

To facilitate software developers in navigating the complexities of bug identification and resolution, bug tracking systems like Bugzilla and Jira play a pivotal role in bug-fixing endeavours. These systems are extensively employed, providing users, including software testers, with a platform to submit bug reports. This facilitates a seamless notification process for software developers, ensuring that identified bugs are promptly addressed ^{[2] [5] [9]}. A standard bug report typically includes critical details such as the time of reporting, severity levels, anomalous program performance, and comprehensive steps to replicate the identified bug. Software developers leverage these bug reports as indispensable resources, utilizing them to discern and rectify reported issues ^[6].

But, these traditional bug tracking tools exhibit certain drawbacks, including a reliance on manual bug resolution, limited automation capabilities, a learning curve for users, overhead in bug reporting, and a focus on tracking rather than correction. These tools heavily depend on user-submitted bug reports, potentially leading to incomplete or inaccurate information. To enhance the bug detection and resolution process,

integration of Sequence-to-Sequence (Seq2Seq) ^[1] models becomes more important. Seq2Seq models operate on the premise of deep neural networks, leveraging advanced machine learning techniques to comprehend and rectify software bugs autonomously.

Models are trained on vast datasets containing pairs of input sequences (buggy code) and corresponding output sequences (corrected code). These training processes enable the Seq2Seq models to decipher coding problems and generate corrected versions seamlessly, allowing them to decipher coding issues and generate corrected versions.

Upon encountering a bug in the software, the Seq2Seq model utilizes its learned knowledge to identify and understand the nature of the issue. It then generates a corrected version of the code by predicting the appropriate sequence of code tokens to rectify the detected bug. This process is akin to the model “translating” the buggy code into a corrected version, drawing parallels to its original application in language translation tasks.

The efficacy of Seq2Seq models in bug correction lies in their ability to capture contextual dependencies, understand the code’s semantics and syntactic structure, and generate meaningful corrections. As a result, these models contribute to a faster and more efficient bug resolution process, reducing the amount of manual work on developers and expediting the overall software development lifecycle.

2 PROPOSED MODEL

The AST Module is responsible for converting the input programs into an Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) ^[4]. It uses a specialized parser to convert the input programs into a structured format that can be easily processed by the other modules in the Seq2SeqModule. This allows the other modules to focus on correcting the input programs without worrying about the complexities of the input programs’ syntax. The AST nodes must be pre-processed by the Data Pre-processing Module before being sent to the Pyramid Encoder Module. The Data Pre-processing Module performs various pre-processing tasks on the AST nodes, such as removing unnecessary nodes, simplifying complex nodes, and normalizing the node values.

The Pyramid Encoder Module is responsible for encoding the pre-processed AST nodes into a sequence of vectors. The Pyramid Encoder Module uses a multi-layer bidirectional recurrent neural network (BiRNN) ^[8] to encode the AST nodes. The BiRNN processes the AST nodes in both forward and backward directions, allowing it to capture the context of the AST nodes more effectively. The Pyramid Encoder Module then outputs a sequence of vectors that represents the encoded AST nodes. Based on the attention mask, the Attention Mechanism Module in the Seq2SeqModule modifies the encoded sequence. AST nodes in the sequence are weighed in accordance with their importance by the Attention Mechanism Module using attention mechanism. This allows the Attention Mechanism Module to focus on the most important AST nodes when generating the corrected program. The Decoder Module in the Seq2SeqModule is responsible for decoding the modified sequence of vectors back into a program. The Decoder Module uses a multi-layer recurrent neural network (RNN) ^[1] to decode the modified sequence of vectors into a program. The RNN processes the modified sequence of vectors in a sequential manner, allowing it to generate the corrected program one token at a time. The Decoder Module then outputs the corrected program as the final output of the Seq2Seq Module.

2.1 DATA PREPROCESSING

This module is responsible for creating datasets aimed at code correction for both testing and training purposes. It takes in a raw dataset focused on code rectification and produces a preprocessed dataset by performing various tasks such as splitting, padding, and tokenizing sequences. Each distinct token is generated by breaking down the source and target code sequences into tokens. To ensure uniformity in the length of tokenized sequences, additional padding tokens are introduced as necessary. Subsequently, a vocabulary is constructed using the most frequently occurring tokens within the dataset. From this dataset, distinct sets for Training, Validation, and Testing are created. The processed data is then loaded into memory for use in both training and testing phases.

Figure 1: block diagram representation of the model

2.2 ABSTRACT SYNTAX TREE (AST)

The AST Module is responsible for converting the input programs into an Abstract Syntax Tree (AST). It contains a Code Reverse Search System (CRSS) for bug localization based on syntactic and semantic information. CRSS Source Files is a reference to the program's original source code files that are being examined for localization errors. The subsequent procedure is Split AST to ST and the source files of Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) are divided into smaller Syntax Trees (ST) ^[3]. This aids in locating the pertinent code segments for a particular bug report.

The Syntax Trees are translated into numerical representations using a ST encoder. This encoding makes it possible to compare and analyse code fragments using machine learning techniques. Sequential input, including encoded syntax trees, is handled by recurrent neural networks (RNNs) equipped with long short-term memory (LSTM) ^[1]. Using LSTM, linkages and patterns between code fragments may be discovered.

Code Representation indicates the stage to provide a single numerical representation of the code fragments, this component combines the encoded STs and LSTM outputs. User input or feedback, such as bug reports or issue descriptions, is referred to here. It is utilised in the process of ranking and comparing the pertinent code fragments.

Word2vec is a technique that uses natural language processing to create vector representations of words. In this case, it acts as an illustration of the textual information included in bug reports, allowing code samples to be compared. Using a variety of methods, including textual information in which Word2vec

representations of text found in code snippets and bug reports are employed, the Semantic and Syntactical Similarity portion assesses the degree of similarity between the code snippets and bug reports. Textual information includes:

Figure 2: AST analysis

Relevance Vector Space Model (rVSM): This technique ranks documents according to how relevant they are to a query. The code snippets are ranked according to their semantic relevance to the issue reports in this particular context.

Token matching: This technique looks for token matches between code fragments and problem reports.

Stack Trace: If accessible, stack traces offer useful details for pinpointing the precise site of the fault or issue.

Combining scores is to provide a thorough rating of the code fragments, the similarity scores from the different approaches are merged. Ranked Files is a list of code fragments that have been ranked according to how relevant they are to the bug report is the result of the CRSS. Similarity integration represents by integrating the CRSS system into their current development workflows, this component helps developers localise bugs more effectively.

2.3 Seq2Seq MODULE

The seq2seq model is an encoder-decoder architecture that is used for sequence-to-sequence learning tasks. the encoder and decoder are both implemented using Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) ^[1]. Through gating mechanisms, GRUs are recurrent neural networks (RNNs) capable of capturing long-range dependencies in sequences.

In the GRU-based seq2seq model, the encoder is implemented using a stack of GRU layers. Each layer in the stack processes a portion of the input sequence, with the layers at the top of the stack processing the most recent parts of the sequence. This allows the encoder to capture both local and global dependencies in the input sequence.

The decoder in the GRU-based seq2seq model is also implemented using a GRU-based decoder. This decoder generates the output sequence by predicting the next token in the sequence based on the current

hidden state and the previously generated tokens. The decoder also uses an attention mechanism to weigh the hidden states of the encoder layers based on the current hidden state of the decoder which allows it to focus on the most relevant parts of the input sequence when generating the output sequence.

2.3.1 PYRAMID ENCODER

The GRU-based seq2seq Pyramid Encoder module is an alternative implementation of the encoder in a seq2seq model. Instead of using a single GRU layer to process the input sequence, this module uses a stack of GRU layers. Each layer

Figure 3: visualization of pyramid encoder [1].

in the stack processes a portion of the input sequence, with the layers at the top of the stack processing the most recent parts of the sequence. Because of its architecture, the encoder may interpret the input sequence in terms of both local and global dependencies.

Consider a multilayer seq2seq encoder, its input at i^{th} layer at step t is $x_t^{(i)}$ and the output is $h_t^{(i)}$ [1]:

$$h_t^{(i)} = \text{Layer}^{(i)}(x_t^{(i)}) \quad (1)$$

In standard seq2seq models, the output of the i^{th} layer $h^{(i)}$ is directly used as input of the $i + 1^{\text{th}}$ layer, $x^{(i+1)}$ [1]:

$$x_t^{(i+1)} = h_t^{(i)} \quad (2)$$

and the time step $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$, the layer number $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ and $x_t^{(i)}$ being the embedded representation of the input instance.

For pyramid encoder, we introduce a pyramid module in between $h^{(i)}$ and $x^{(i+1)}$ as Eq. 3 follows [1]:

$$x_t^{(i+1)} = \tanh(W_{\text{pyr}}(h_{2t}^{(i)}, h_{2t+1}^{(i)}) + b_{\text{pyr}}) \quad (3)$$

This pyramid encoder module reduces the length of the input $x^{(i)}$ by half with each application and the final output length of the encoder will be $T/2^{N-1}$. The pyramid structure will extract crucial information while minimizing redundant data from neighbouring hidden states, thereby reducing training expenses while maintaining correction accuracy. This concept bears resemblance to convolution, albeit without the use of filters.

The GRU models used a multi-layer bidirectional GRU and incorporated a pyramid encoder [1]:

$$f_t^{(i)} = \text{GRU}(f_{t-1}^{(i)}, x_t^{(i)}) \quad (4)$$

$$b_t^{(i)} = \text{GRU}(b_{t+1}^{(i)}, x_t^{(i)}) \quad (5)$$

$$h_t^{(i)} = f_t^{(i)} + b_t^{(i)} \quad (6)$$

$$x_t^{(i+1)} = \tanh(W_{\text{pyr}}(h_{2t}^{(i)}, h_{2t+1}^{(i)}) + b_{\text{pyr}}) \quad (7)$$

where $x_t^{(i+1)}$ denotes the input to next layer, $f_t^{(i)}$ and $b_t^{(i)}$ denote output from a forward and a backward GRU, respectively. The GRU (Gated Recurrent Unit) is a type of Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) model that incorporates a gating mechanism to regulate information flow, enhancing its ability to capture long-term dependencies in sequential data. The reset gate controls how much of the previous hidden state to ignore, while the update gate determines how much of the new candidate hidden state to incorporate. The candidate hidden state is computed based on the input and previous hidden state, scaled by the reset gate. Finally, the actual hidden state is updated using a combination of the candidate hidden state and the previous hidden state, controlled by the update gate. These operations enable the GRU model to effectively capture and retain relevant information over long sequences, addressing the challenges of vanishing gradients and facilitating more efficient learning in sequential data processing tasks.

2.3.2 ATTENTION MECHANISM

Rather of depending entirely on the encoder's final hidden state, which might not fully capture every essential detail in the input sequence, the attention strategy assists the decoder in preferentially focusing on the most pertinent portions of the sequence. By focusing on distinct segments of the input sequence according to the attention scores, this method enables the decoder to produce an output sequence that is more accurate and specifically relevant. To calculate attention scores, feed-forward neural networks are frequently used, and the proposed model is based on them. To calculate attention scores, hidden states are passed through the attention mechanism of the encoder and decoder layers. To generate the output token, the weighted sum of the input sequence is computed using the attention scores. The four attention mechanisms used include:

- Bahdanau Attention: Using this algorithm, attention weights are calculated by calculating the dot product of the decoder state and each input element, which is a form of additive attention mechanism. This process yields a probability distribution over the input elements.

- Luong Dot Attention: Dot product attention mechanisms calculate attention weights by developing a probability distribution over input elements using the dot product of the state of the decoder and each input.
- Luong General Attention: An attention mechanism based on the dot product of the decoder state and each input element is used to calculate attention weights. A softmax activation function is applied to this neural network to obtain a probability distribution over the input elements by passing the dot product of the decoder state and each input element through a feedforward neural network with one hidden layer.
- Luong Concat Attention: The decoder state and each input element are concatenated in this type of concatenative attention mechanism, and a softmax activation function is applied to the input elements to obtain a probability distribution. The data is then passed through a feedforward neural network with one hidden layer.

These attention mechanisms enable the GRU model to accommodate longer input sequences and produce more accurate results by enabling it to concentrate on various elements of the input sequence while creating the output sequence.

2.3.3 DECODER

The GRU models utilize a regular multilayer unidirectional GRU. The decoder generates the output sequence by iterating over each time step in the input sequence and generating an output token for each time step. The generated output tokens are then combined into a single output sequence.

Figure 4: plot of memory usage with Bahdanau attention [1]. The pyramid encoder shows higher memory efficiency with only small increase in memory occupied.

3 MODEL PARAMETERS

Three layers of bidirectional encoder were used all three layers have 400 hidden states. Decoding was done with a 3-layer unidirectional decoder with 400 hidden states.

4 RESULTS

The paper successfully demonstrated the applicability of seq2seq models for code correction. The incorporation of Abstract Syntax Trees (ASTs) into the model allowed for a deeper understanding of code structure, facilitating the identification and correction of syntactic errors. Furthermore, the implementation of a pyramid encoder architecture enhanced the model's efficiency in processing code sequences. The decoder, coupled with an attention mechanism, effectively generated corrected code by focusing on relevant portions of the AST during the correction process.

4.1 DATASETS

The Juliet Test Suite for C/C++ (v1.2) developed by NSA Centre was used in this study. Total 61,387 test cases are included in this collection, including instances of defective code and instances of fixed code. There are hundreds of sample code instances in each of the more than 100 Common Weakness Enumerations (CWEs) included in these test cases. We observe that there is a substantial amount of dead code in the instances. We eliminate the dead code to give the code a more genuine feel. It was discovered that several code instances included “if conditions” that cause one branch to be executed in the case of the defective code instance and the other to be executed in the case of the fixed instance. We eliminated these cases since they are not practical. Additionally, we renamed the functions. We were left with 31,082 pairs of good-bad code occurrences after the pre-processing.

5 CONCLUSION

Seq2seq models equipped with ASTs, pyramid encoders, decoders, and attention mechanisms offer a promising avenue for automatic code correction. Compared to traditional rule-based methods, this deep learning approach demonstrates the potential for handling complex code errors and adapting to evolving programming languages. Future research could investigate the effectiveness of different encoder/decoder architectures and explore the application of more sophisticated attention mechanisms to further enhance the model's accuracy and generalizability.

REFERENCES

- [1] Shan Huang, Xiao Zhou, and Sang Chin. *Application of seq2seq models on code correction*. *Frontiers in artificial intelligence*, 4:590215, 2021.
- [2] Bin Li, Ying Wei, Xiaobing Sun, Lili Bo, Dingshan Chen, and Chuanqi Tao. “Towards the identification of bug entities and relations in bug reports”. *Automated Software Engineering*, 29(1):24, 2022.
- [3] Zhen Li, Deqing Zou, Shouhuai Xu, Hai Jin, Yawei Zhu, and Zhaoxuan Chen. “Sysevr: A framework for using deep learning to detect software vulnerabilities”. *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, 19(4):2244–2258, 2021.
- [4] Hongliang Liang, Lu Sun, Meilin Wang, and Yuxing Yang. “Deep learning with customized abstract syntax tree for bug localization”. *IEEE Access*, 7:116309–116320, 2019.
- [5] Jinting Lu, Xiaobing Sun, Bin Li, Lili Bo, and Tao Zhang. “Beat: Considering question types for bug question answering via templates”. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 225:107098, 2021.
- [6] Stacy K Lukins, Nicholas A Kraft, and Letha H Etzkorn. “Bug localization using latent dirichlet allocation”. *Information and Software Technology*, 52(9):972–990, 2010.
- [7] Xiaobing Sun, Tianchi Zhou, Rongcun Wang, Yucong Duan, Lili Bo, and Jianming Chang. “Experience report: investigating bug fixes in machine learning frameworks/libraries”. *Frontiers of Computer Science*, 15:1–16, 2021.

- [8] Jinwei Wan, Bo Chen, Yingqi Liu, Yijun Yuan, Hongwei Liu, and Lin Jin. "Recognizing the hrrp by combining cnn and birnn with attention mechanism". *IEEE Access*, 8:20828–20837, 2020.
- [9] Wenjin Wu, Wen Zhang, Ye Yang, and Qing Wang. "Drex: Developer recommendation with k-nearest-neighbor search and expertise ranking". In *2011 18th Asia-Pacific Software Engineering Conference*, pages 389–396. IEEE, 2011.